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Title: Reduction of Hand-Arm Vibrations (HAV) when driving electric scooters

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Abstract

With a view to sustainable mobility, it has been noted in recent years that an ever-increasing number of users are using electric scooters as a means of transport to travel short distances [1-2]. The use of such means exposes users to mechanical vibrations, both transmitted to the whole body (WBVs) [3] and to the hand-arm group (HAVs) [4-5]. Exposure to vibrations while riding electric scooters is usually not a problem for human health as the exposure times are very short. However, these vehicles are also used by workers to make home deliveries. In the latter case, the times of exposure to mechanical vibrations can become relevant for human health.

In this paper, the daily exposure to HAVs during electric scooter use was estimated by performing in-situ experimental test. In particular, first, the HAVs were acquired using low-cost instrumentation, and then they were analyzed both in the time domain, taking into account the requirements contained in the UNI EN ISO 5349 standard [4-5], and in the frequency domain, considering the amplitude of the Power Spectral Density (PSD) in the most significant frequency range for the hand-arm group. Furthermore, the same tests were performed by replacing the stock handle with a 3D printed handle (Italian Patent No. 102021000004691 filed on 16.03.2023, International Patent Application No. PCT/IB2022/051673 filed on 25/02/2022). The results show that using the 3D printed handle allows for a reduction in daily exposure to HAVs such as increasing the maximum exposure time by 20%.

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